

ammonium N in floodwater is controlled by the pH of floodwater.

We measured the pH, ammonium N, and nitrate N of floodwater with integrated organic-inorganic N management. The experimental loam soil (Mollisol of Tarai of northern India) had pH (1:1) 7.6, EC (1:1) 0.115 dS/m, 2.03% organic C, 0.21% total N, 7.4 ppm available ammonium N, and 12.2 ppm available NO₃⁻-N

Floodwater ammonium N peaked at 3 d after transplanting (DT) in 1982-83 and at 7 DT in 1983-84. Thereafter, it decreased and was not found in either year at 30 DT (see figure).

The low concentration of floodwater ammonium N is attributed to floodwater pH, in turn controlled by partial pressure of CO₂. Higher concentration of ammonium N in 1983-84 over 1982-83 is also attributed to floodwater pH, as pH at the initial dates after transplanting was higher in 1983-84 (see figure).

Nitrate N peaked at 9 DT and

Floodwater pH, NH₄⁺-N, and NO₃⁻-N with respect to time in lowland rice. Nainital, U.P., India.

reached zero at 30 DT both years. However, its concentration was more than that of ammonium N, probably because of nitrification in the transitional zone of the flooded soil water system.

Results show that floodwater pH, ammonium N, and nitrate N can be kept at lower levels by using organic N sources (green manure and farmyard manure) as part of integrated N management. □

Efficiency of modified urea granules in transplanted rice

T. V. R. Prasad, M. M. Hosmani, L. S. Devi, and K. R. Kulkarni, Agronomic Research Project, University of Agricultural Sciences, GKVK, Bangalore 560065, India

We tested efficiency of modified urea granules in transplanted rice in farmers' fields, Bangalore district, Karnataka, India, in monsoon 1986.

Seven treatments (see table) were tried

in 10 randomly selected fields, using cultivar Mandya Vani (140-d duration) in clay to clay loam soils. The soils had pH 6.6, EC of 0.18 dS/m at 25 °C, 489 kg available N/ha, 14.2 kg P/ha, and 285.4 kg K/ha. A common dose of 22 kg P and 42 kg K/ha was applied in a plot 50 m².

At 56 kg N/ha, urea supergranule (USG) was superior (29.6% more yield), followed by rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU, 24.2%), large urea granule (LGU, 18.6%), and gypsum-coated urea

(GCU, 16.7%). Modified urea granules may provide more efficient N utilization, shown by higher harvest index (ratio of yield to total biomass), more panicles per m² at harvest, and more filled grains per panicle (see table).

In yield per kg of added N, USG was best, followed by RPCU, LGU, and GCU, all superior to prilled urea (PU) at 56 and 84 kg N/ha. Cost-wise, PU equals LGU, with others equal to or 10-20% higher than PU. □

Effect of modified urea granules on grain yield and yield attributes.^a Bangalore, India, 1986 wet season.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)	Response ^c (kg grain/kg N)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains/panicle	Harvest index	Biomass (t/ha)
T1 No N	3.60 g	—	14.3 g	97 cde	0.44 e	8.5 g
T2 PU ^d	4.51 f	16.2	89.3 f	101 cd	0.46 d	10.3 f
T3 LGU (45% N) ^e	5.35 bcd	31.2	105.9 abc	121 a	0.48 c	11.3 abc
T4 RPCU (36.4% N, 1.85% P) ^e	5.60 abc	35.7	109.4 a	103 c	0.52 a	11.0 abcde
T5 GCU (36.5% N, 4.4% Ca, 3.4% S) ^e	5.26 de	29.6	103.8 abcd	115 ab	0.48 c	11.1 abcd
T6 USG (45% N) ^f	5.85 a	40.1	108.0 ab	121 a	0.52 a	11.4 ab
T7 PU ^d	5.63 ab	24.2	101.3 cde	121 a	0.50 b	11.6 a

^aColumn means followed by common letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bT2 - T6 at 56 kg N/ha, T7 at 84 kg N/ha. ^cOver 0 kg N/ha. ^dApplied in 3 equal splits: basal, 30 and 50 d after transplanting. ^eBasal broadcast incorporation. ^fPlacement after planting.